

Magnetic Mesoporous Silica Nanocomposites based on SBA-15/Fe₃O₄ as Multifunctional Nanoplatforams for Technological Applications

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ABSTRACT

Magnetic-mesoporous silica nanocomposite materials are emerging as one of the most appealing candidates to produce novel nanodevices with superior textural and magnetic properties. Their use as catalysts, adsorbents, gas storage and sensors have gained increasing importance¹. Particularly in biomedicine, their applications include MRI, magnetic hyperthermia, controlled drug release, bone tissue engineering, theranostics² and local cancer treatment³. These nanocomposites possess outstanding combined features providing a multifunctional activity⁴. On the one hand, SBA-15 mesoporous silica has a flat two-dimensional hexagonal symmetry with an ordered cylindrical pore channels system, which are highly interconnected. Moreover, SBA-15 shows remarkable hydrothermal and chemical stability, making it suitable for hosting and protecting important sensible molecules such as DNA, genes, enzymes, etc. Its surface plenty of silanol groups confers the ability of being easily modified by using organosilane species. On the other hand, the incorporation of superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) add different beneficial effects related to their nanosize and magnetic properties like magnetic stimulation on biological media (i.e., enhancement of cell adhesion, proliferation and differentiation), localized heat release by magnetic hyperthermia⁵, reinforcement of the SBA-15 mechanical properties. Besides, the presence of SPIONs confer the nanocomposites the capacity to be magnetically recovered from different environments as well as function as catalyst for Fenton reaction that can be used to degrade pollutants.

In this talk, different magnetic mesoporous materials^{4,6}, obtained by optimized synthetic methods and different in situ or ex situ approaches of magnetic doping, with chemically tailored morphological, textural and magnetic responses will be presented. TEM images of figures 1A and 1B display two different examples of magnetic mesoporous nanocomposites, where the magnetic nanoparticles are attached to the external silica surface, showing that they conserve the morphology and hexagonal symmetric disposition as their SBA-15 mesoporous silica precursor. N₂ adsorption analysis reveals surface areas above 200 m²/g, which are higher than those of conventional ceramics, ensuring an enhanced capacity for loading a large amount of molecules of different nature. XRD patterns reveal the conventional reflections associated with the SBA-15 type materials (low angle) as well as the presence of crystalline magnetite in these nanocomposites (figure 2A and 2B). The magnetization cycles show no hysteresis or coercive forces (figure 3), which is highly desirable for several applications to avoid magnetic agglomeration of particles. In addition, hyperthermia characterizations have been performed to assess the magneto-thermal abilities of some representative samples. The hyperthermia response can be tuned by varying both the content of magnetite and the location of magnetite on the (SBA-15/Fe₃O₄) composite system, as evidenced in figure 4. Negligible temperature increase (low magnetite content/magnetite inside SBA-15 mesopores) or a high increase of about 40° C in only one minute (high magnetite content/magnetite attached to external SBA-15 surface) can be obtained. Finally, the easiness of having organically modified surfaces with different functional groups provide them additional properties and features by incorporating, for example, fluorescent-labeling and antibody-bioconjugation.

Keywords: Magnetic mesoporous nanocomposites, magnetite, multiples functionalities, outstanding features, SBA-15, several applications.

Figure 1. TEM images of the magnetic mesoporous nanocomposites A) Magnetic aggregates ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@\text{C}$) attached to external SBA-15 surface B) Magnetic NPs ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@\text{SiO}_2$) attached to external SBA-15 surface.

Figure 2. A) Low-angle XRD patterns and B) XRD patterns of the magnetic mesoporous nanocomposites. The expected peaks for magnetite (JCPDS card No. 19-0629) are also indicated at the bottom of the figures and the different peaks have been labelled with their corresponding Miller indexes.

Figure 3. Hysteresis loops of the magnetic mesoporous nanocomposites up to 10 kOe. HMC = High magnetite content LMC = Low magnetite content

Figure 4. Heating curves of the magnetic mesoporous nanocomposites.

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

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